

DAMPING OPTIMIZATION OF LAMINATED PLATES BASED ON COMPLEX MODULUS APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

The present paper deals with the damping characteristics of symmetrically laminated plates. First, the effect of laminate configuration on the damping characteristics is investigated for cantilevered laminated plates. To examine the effect of laminate configuration, the concept of complex modulus is introduced and the damping characteristics are represented on the lamination parameter plane, where the complex stiffness invariants are newly proposed in this paper. Next, the optimal laminate configurations for the cantilevered laminated plates with maximal damping subjected to the constraints on the natural frequencies are determined by using Nelder-Mead downhill simplex method in which lamination parameters are used as intermediate design variables. The relation between the laminate configurations and the damping characteristics is discussed based on the concept of lamination parameters.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, advanced composite materials have been applied to aerospace structures. Damping is an important parameter related to the study of dynamic behavior of fiber reinforced composite structures. It is well known that the flexural vibration of flexible structural components may cause the fatigue failures, and the passive vibration suppression with material damping can be effective. Therefore, structural design considering vibrational damping properties is an indispensable technology for improving vibration characteristics of structures. So far, a lot of research has been carried out from the viewpoints of predicting damping capacities at macro-mechanical level and its optimization [1-7].

The present paper deals with the damping characteristics of symmetrically laminated plates. First, the effect of laminate configuration on the damping characteristics is investigated for cantilevered laminated plates. To examine the effect of laminate configuration, the concept of complex modulus is introduced and the damping characteristics are represented on the lamination parameter plane, where the complex stiffness invariants are newly proposed in this paper. Next, the optimal laminate configurations for the cantilevered laminated plates with maximal damping subjected to the constraints on the natural frequencies are determined by using Nelder-Mead downhill simplex method in which lamination parameters are used as intermediate design variables, instead of ply fiber orientation angles and ply thicknesses.

2 DAMPING CHARACTERISTICS OF SYMMETRICALLY LAMINATED PLATES

2.1 Fundamental Equations

The finite element formulation for damping characteristics of cantilevered laminated plate shown in Fig. 1 can be described as follows:

$$\left([K^*(f)] - \lambda_i [M] \right) \{ \phi_i \} = \{ 0 \} \quad (1)$$

where the mass and complex stiffness matrices are denoted by M and K^* , the frequency is denoted by f , the eigenvalue and eigenvector of the i -th vibration mode are denoted by λ_i and ϕ_i ,

Figure 1: Cantilevered laminated plates ($L = c = 200$ mm, $h = 2.0$ mm).

respectively. The complex eigenvalue problem gives the natural angular frequency and modal loss factor of the i -th vibration mode, ω_i and η_i , as follows:

$$\omega_i (= 2\pi f_i) = \sqrt{\operatorname{Re}(\lambda_i)}, \quad \eta_i (= 2\zeta_i) = \frac{\operatorname{Im}(\lambda_i)}{\operatorname{Re}(\lambda_i)}, \quad (2)$$

where the real and imaginary parts are denoted by $\operatorname{Re}(\)$ and $\operatorname{Im}(\)$, respectively. The natural frequency and modal damping ratio of the i -th vibration mode are denoted by f_i and ζ_i , respectively.

In classical lamination theory, the constitutive equation of symmetrically laminated plate can be described as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A^* & 0 \\ 0 & D^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where the generalized stress components are: $N = \{N_x, N_y, N_{xy}\}^T$, $M = \{M_x, M_y, M_{xy}\}^T$, and the generalized strain components are: $\varepsilon = \{\varepsilon_x, \varepsilon_y, \varepsilon_{xy}\}^T$, $\kappa = \{\kappa_x, \kappa_y, \kappa_{xy}\}^T$, respectively. The in-plane and out-of-plane complex stiffnesses are denoted by A_{ij}^* ($i, j = 1, 2, 6$) and D_{ij}^* ($i, j = 1, 2, 6$), respectively. In case of symmetrically laminated plates chosen in a practical usage, the in-plane and out-of-plane problems are separated each other, and the out-of-plane problem is dominated by only the out-of-plane complex stiffness components D_{ij}^* .

The out-of-plane complex stiffness components D_{ij}^* ($i, j = 1, 2, 6$) in the complex stiffness matrix K^* can be described by using the complex stiffness invariants U_i^* ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$), proposed in the present paper, and the out-of-plane lamination parameters ξ_i ($i = 9, 10, 11, 12$) as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} D_{11}^* \\ D_{22}^* \\ D_{12}^* \\ D_{66}^* \\ D_{16}^* \\ D_{26}^* \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{h^3}{12} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \xi_9 & \xi_{10} & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -\xi_9 & \xi_{10} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_{10} & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_{10} & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \xi_{11}/2 & \xi_{12} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_{11}/2 & -\xi_{12} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} U_1^* \\ U_2^* \\ U_3^* \\ U_4^* \\ U_5^* \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where

$$\begin{Bmatrix} U_1^* \\ U_2^* \\ U_3^* \\ U_4^* \\ U_5^* \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 3/8 & 3/8 & 1/4 & 1/2 \\ 1/2 & -1/2 & 0 & 0 \\ 1/8 & 1/8 & -1/4 & -1/2 \\ 1/8 & 1/8 & 3/4 & -1/2 \\ 1/8 & 1/8 & -1/4 & 1/2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} Q_{11}^* \\ Q_{22}^* \\ Q_{12}^* \\ Q_{66}^* \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

The thickness of the plate is denoted by h . According to the elastic-viscoelastic correspondence principle, the on-axis complex stiffness components are denoted by Q_{ij}^* ($i, j = 1, 2, 6$), which are obtained by using five complex engineering constants of a unidirectional lamina E_L^* , E_T^* , G_{LT}^* , ν_{LT}^* and ν_{TL}^* as follows:

$$Q_{11}^* = \frac{E_L^*}{1 - \nu_{LT}^* \nu_{TL}^*}, \quad Q_{22}^* = \frac{E_T^*}{1 - \nu_{LT}^* \nu_{TL}^*}, \quad Q_{12}^* = \nu_{LT}^* Q_{22}^* = \nu_{TL}^* Q_{11}^*, \quad Q_{66}^* = G_{LT}^*, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} E_L^* &= E_L \{1 + i\eta_{E_L}(f)\}, & E_T^* &= E_T \{1 + i\eta_{E_T}(f)\}, \\ G_{LT}^* &= G_{LT} \{1 + i\eta_{G_{LT}}(f)\}, & \nu_{LT}^* &= \nu_{LT} \{1 + i\eta_{\nu_{LT}}(f)\}, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

and $i = \sqrt{-1}$. By defining the non-dimensional coordinate along the thickness denoted by $u (= z/(h/2))$, lamination parameters can be expressed as the following forms, using a symmetric condition at the mid-plane [8]:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_9 &= 3 \int_0^1 \cos 2\theta(u) u^2 du, & \xi_{10} &= 3 \int_0^1 \cos 4\theta(u) u^2 du, \\ \xi_{11} &= 3 \int_0^1 \sin 2\theta(u) u^2 du, & \xi_{12} &= 3 \int_0^1 \sin 4\theta(u) u^2 du, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where a distribution function of fiber orientation angle through the thickness is denoted by $\theta(u)$. Lamination parameters are functionals of the function $\theta(u)$ as shown in Eq. (8). When the layer angle distribution is specified through the thickness, the lamination parameters can be determined uniquely from Eq. (8), and the out-of-plane stiffness components can be determined from Eq. (4). The out-of-plane complex stiffness components D_{ij}^* in the complex stiffness matrix K^* can be described by using the four out-of-plane lamination parameters, as stated above. Therefore, the four out-of-plane lamination parameters govern the damping characteristics of laminated plates.

It is well known that the lamination parameters are not independent. The relation among four out-of-plane lamination parameters can be expressed as follows [9]:

$$2(1 + \xi_{10}) \xi_{11}^2 - 4\xi_9 \xi_{11} \xi_{12} + \xi_{12}^2 \leq (\xi_{10} - 2\xi_9^2 + 1)(1 - \xi_{10}). \quad (9)$$

From Eq. (9), the feasible region of (ξ_9, ξ_{10}) for $D_{16}^* = D_{26}^* = 0$, i.e. $(\xi_{11}, \xi_{12}) = (0, 0)$ can be obtained as

$$2\xi_9^2 - 1 \leq \xi_{10} \leq 1. \quad (10)$$

The feasible region of coupling lamination parameters for the fixed values of (ξ_9, ξ_{10}) is also given in Eq. (9). For instance, the feasible region of (ξ_{11}, ξ_{12}) for $(\xi_9, \xi_{10}) = (0, 0)$ can be obtained as

$$2\xi_{11}^2 + \xi_{12}^2 \leq 1. \quad (11)$$

On the lamination parameter plane $\xi_{11} - \xi_{12}$, the feasible region is within the ellipse and (ξ_{11}, ξ_{12})

Table 1: Material properties of GFRP.

E_L	E_T	G_{LT}	ν_{LT}	ρ
[GPa]	[GPa]	[GPa]		[kg/m ³]
57.85	19.86	6.1	0.264	2000

Figure 2: Frequency-dependent material loss factors.

governs the bending-torsional coupling as shown in Eq. (4).

On the contrary, when the four out-of-plane lamination parameters are specified to satisfy Eq. (9), the corresponding laminate configurations must be determined. Though a number of candidates of laminate configurations can correspond to the given lamination parameters, one of the corresponding laminate configurations, expressed as $\left[(\theta_1)_{hp1} / (\theta_2)_{hp2} / (\theta_3)_{hp3} / (\theta_4)_{hp4} \right]_s$, can be determined based on a method for determining laminate configurations [10], where the subscript hpi denotes the thickness ratio of the ply with respect to the half of the thickness of the plate.

2.2 Numerical Results and Discussion

The effect of laminate configuration on the damping characteristics is investigated for cantilevered laminated plates shown in Fig. 1. As a numerical example, the material properties of GFRP (S-2 glass/3501-6) described in Table 1 and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \eta_{E_L}(f) &= 5.15 \times 10^{-7} f + 5.99 \times 10^{-3}, \\
 \eta_{E_T}(f) &= 8.37 \times 10^{-4} \ln(f) + 4.07 \times 10^{-3}, \\
 \eta_{G_{LT}}(f) &= 25.5 \times 10^{-4} f - 50.37 \times 10^{-4},
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

are used [11]. Here, the complex Poisson's ratio ν_{LT}^* is assumed to be frequency-independent, and then is real constant value. The material loss factors shown above are presented graphically in Fig. 2. In the present paper, 20 x 20 elements are used for structural analysis, where the four-node rectangular plate-bending element is employed.

Fig. 3 shows the contours of the loss factor of the first vibration mode, which corresponds to the first bending vibration mode, η_1 on the lamination parameter plane. In Fig. 3(a), the contours of the loss factor are represented on the lamination parameter plane $\xi_9 - \xi_{10}$ at $(\xi_{11}, \xi_{12}) = (0.0, 0.0)$. From this figure, we can clarify the relation between principal-axis stiffness and damping characteristics. The loss factor increases when the value of ξ_9 decreases or that of ξ_{10} increases. The lamination parameters, (ξ_9, ξ_{10}) , which maximize the loss factor, appears at $(\xi_9, \xi_{10}) = (-1.0, 1.0)$, and the corresponding laminate configuration is a 90 unidirectional laminate. The lamination parameters, (ξ_9, ξ_{10}) , which minimize the loss factor, appears at $(\xi_9, \xi_{10}) = (0.0, -1.0)$, and the corresponding

(a) $\xi_9 - \xi_{10}$ plane for $(\xi_{11}, \xi_{12}) = (0, 0)$.

(b) $\xi_{11} - \xi_{12}$ plane for $(\xi_9, \xi_{10}) = (0, 0)$.

Figure 3: Contours of loss factor of the first vibration mode η_1 [%] on the lamination parameter plane.

laminate configuration is a +45/-45 angle-ply laminate. In Fig. 3(b), the contours of the loss factor are represented on the lamination parameter plane $\xi_{11} - \xi_{12}$ at $(\xi_9, \xi_{10}) = (0.0, 0.0)$. From this figure, we can clarify the relation between bending-torsional coupling and damping characteristics. The loss factor decreases when the values of (ξ_{11}, ξ_{12}) increases with the same sign. Fig. 4 shows the contours of the natural frequency of the first vibration mode f_1 on the lamination parameter plane. From this figure, it is clarified that the range of f_1 is from 25 to 45 Hz for the cantilevered laminated plates with the laminate configurations corresponding to the lamination parameters within the feasible region in this figure. In Fig. 2, the values of the material loss factor $\eta_{G_{LT}}$ are smaller than those of the other material loss factors η_{E_L} and η_{E_T} in the frequency range. Therefore, the loss factor of the first vibration mode η_1 decreases when the value of ξ_{10} decreases and torsional stiffness D_{66}^* becomes larger, and the contours of the loss factor are not similar to reversal of the contours of natural frequency of the first vibration mode f_1 in Fig. 3(a). These results indicate that the frequency-dependent material loss factors of GFRP as described by Eq. (12) and shown in Fig. 2 affect the damping characteristics of laminated plates.

(b) $\xi_{11} - \xi_{12}$ plane for $(\xi_9, \xi_{10}) = (0, 0)$.Figure 4: Contours of natural frequency of the first vibration mode f_1 [Hz] on the lamination parameter plane.

3 LAY-UP OPTIMIZATION OF SYMMETRICALLY LAMINATED PLATES FOR DAMPING CHARACTERISTICS

3.1 Formulation of Optimization Problem

Next, we obtain the laminate configurations to maximize the damping of symmetrically laminated plates as shown in Fig. 1 under the constraints on the natural frequencies. To obtain the optimal laminate configurations without any limitation on laminate configuration, lamination parameters are used as intermediate design variables, and the optimal laminate configuration can be obtained by a method for determining laminate configurations corresponding to the optimal lamination parameters [10].

The optimization problem can be stated as follows:

$$\text{maximize } \eta_i(\xi_9, \xi_{10}, \xi_{11}, \xi_{12}) \quad (13.a)$$

$$\text{subject to } \xi_9^2 + \xi_{11}^2 \leq 1 \quad (13.b)$$

Table 2: Optimization results.

Case ^a	Optimal lamination parameters				η_1 [%]	f_1 [Hz]	Optimal laminate configuration
	ξ_9	ξ_{10}	ξ_{11}	ξ_{12}			
Baseline	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.599	32.94	quasi-isotropic
I	-1.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.679	25.64	$[90.0_{1.00}]_s$
II	-0.285	0.877	0.249	-0.145	0.637	32.91	$[7.2_{0.14}/82.8_{0.86}]_s$

^a Case I, without any natural frequency constraints, case II, with a natural frequency constraint.

$$\left(\xi_{10} - \xi_9^2 + \xi_{11}^2\right)^2 + \left(\xi_{12} - 2\xi_9\xi_{11}\right)^2 \leq \left(1 - \xi_9^2 - \xi_{11}^2\right)^2 \quad (13.c)$$

$$f_i(\xi_9, \xi_{10}, \xi_{11}, \xi_{12}) = f_{0,i} \quad (13.d)$$

where the Eqs. (13.b), (13.c) correspond to constraints on the feasible region of lamination parameters [9]. Eq. (13.d) corresponds to constraint on the target natural frequency of the i -th vibration mode, which is denoted by $f_{0,i}$.

3.2 Application of Nelder-Mead Downhill Simplex Method to Lay-up Optimization

In the present paper, Nelder-Mead downhill simplex method [12] is adopted as an optimization method. To handle the constraints with this optimization method, the constrained optimization problem needs to be transformed into an unconstrained problem. To ensure the constraint conditions Eqs. (13.b) and (13.c), the coordinates of vertex which violates the above constraint conditions are repaired, and a vertex which is out of the feasible region is moved to the nearest boundary of the feasible region by force. Moreover, the exterior penalty function method is adopted to introduce a natural frequency constraint, Eq. (13.d). Finally, modified objective function $\bar{\eta}$ to be maximized concerning an equality constraint on the target natural frequency is defined as follows:

$$\bar{\eta} = \eta_i - P \times \max\left(\left|1 - \frac{f_i}{f_{0,i}}\right| - \delta, 0\right), \quad (14)$$

where the penalty parameter is denoted by P , and δ is the small positive number, which is set to 10^{-3} in this paper.

The reflection coefficient α , contraction coefficient β and expansion coefficient γ are set to 1.0, 0.5 and 2.0, respectively, as the strategy of this optimization method. Three trials were run for each optimization changing seeds for random numbers to give different initial simplex.

3.3 Numerical Results and Discussion

To investigate the effectiveness of lay-up optimization and that of natural frequency constraint on the increase of loss factor, we examine two optimization problems. The case I is for obtaining the optimal laminate configuration without any natural frequency constraints. The case II is for obtaining the optimal laminate configuration with a natural frequency constraint. The dimensions and material properties of plate are same with those in the above example in the previous chapter. The values of the natural frequency of the i -th vibration mode for a quasi-isotropic laminate, named as baseline laminate, are set to be the target natural frequency $f_{0,i}$, i.e. 32.94 Hz for the first mode.

Table 2 shows the lamination parameters, the corresponding laminate configurations and the loss factor of the first vibration mode of the optimal structures, where the results for cases I and II are compared. This table indicates that the optimal lamination parameters exist on the boundary of the feasible region on the $\xi_9 - \xi_{12}$ coordinates for cases I and II, which represents the optimal laminate configurations consisting of at most two different fiber orientation angles. It is also found that the loss factor of the first vibration mode can be increased by a lay-up optimization. By comparing the results

for cases I and II, it is also found that effect of lay-up optimization on the increase of loss factor becomes small by considering natural frequency constraint in the optimization problem, however, bending-torsional coupling is still effective on the increase of loss factor produced by a lay-up optimization.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effect of principal-axis stiffness and bending-torsional coupling on the damping characteristics of cantilevered symmetrically laminated plates have been studied by introducing the complex stiffness invariants, proposed in this paper, in addition to the concept of lamination parameters. It has been shown that bending-torsional coupling decreases the loss factor as compared with those of a specially orthotropic laminate without coupling due to the frequency-dependent material loss factors of GFRP chosen as the present numerical example.

A lay-up optimization of cantilevered symmetrically laminated plates for maximum damping subjected to the constraints on the natural frequencies has also been conducted by using Nelder-Mead downhill simplex method in this paper. In this optimization problem, lamination parameters are used as intermediate design variables to obtain the optimal laminate configurations without any limitation on the laminate configuration. The optimal lamination parameters exist in the neighborhood of the boundary of the feasible region on the $\xi_9 - \xi_{12}$ coordinates, which represents the optimal laminate configurations consisting of at most two different fiber orientation angles.

REFERENCES

- [1] Chandra, R., Singh, S.P. and Gupta, K., Damping studies in fiber-reinforced composites – a review, *Composite Structures*, **46**, 1999, pp. 41-51.
- [2] Treviso, A., Van Genechten, B., Mundo, D. and Tournour, M., Damping in composite materials: properties and models, *Composites: Part B*, **78**, 2015, pp. 144-152.
- [3] Hashin, Z., Complex moduli of viscoelastic composites – II fiber reinforced materials, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **6**, 1970, pp. 797-807.
- [4] Koo, K.N. and Lee, I., Vibration and damping analysis of composite laminates using shear deformable finite element, *AIAA Journal*, **31**, 1993, pp. 728-735.
- [5] Li, J. and Narita, Y., Analysis and optimal design for the damping property of laminated viscoelastic plates under general edge conditions, *Composites: Part B*, **45**, 2013, pp. 972-980.
- [6] Kameyama, M. and Arai, M., Optimal design of symmetrically laminated plates for damping characteristics using lamination parameters, *Composite Structures*, **132**, 2015, pp. 885-897.
- [7] Kameyama, M., Takahashi, A. and Arai, M., Damping optimization of symmetrically laminated plates with transverse shear deformation using lamination parameters, *Advanced Composite Materials*, **28**, 2019, pp. 1-26.
- [8] Tsai, S.W. and Hahn, H.T., *Introduction to composite materials*, Technomic Publishing, Lancaster, PA, 1980.
- [9] Fukunaga, H. and Sekine, H., Stiffness design method of symmetric laminates using lamination parameters, *AIAA Journal*, **30**, 1992, pp. 2791-2793.
- [10] Fukunaga, H. and Sekine, H., A laminate design for elastic properties of symmetric laminates with extension – shear or bending – twisting coupling, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **28**, 1994, pp. 708-731.
- [11] Crane, R.M. and Gillespie, J.W. Jr., Analytical model for prediction of the damping loss factor of composite materials, *Polymer Composites*, **13**, 1992, pp. 179-190.
- [12] Nelder, J.A. and Mead, R., A simplex method for function minimization, *Computer Journal*, **7**, 1964, pp. 308-313.